

METAPHORICAL POLYTHEORY

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ABSTRACT. Axiomatic theories T of the same structure may differ in the size of their proofs of the same fact. In an elegant, laconic axiomatics, even the simplest theorems may require very long derivations, or statements about comparatively small objects will be accompanied by proofs of monstrous size. As a supposed way around such problems, the idea of metaphorical polytheory is proposed: the original theory T with large proofs is broken down into strictly smaller fragments $T'_i, i \in I$; each T'_i is associated with a fragment U'_i of some theory U_i (metaphor), responsible for its own piece of the theory T ; each U_i has its own system of axioms; by means of the “general logic of fragments” the original T appears as a theory of many axiomatics and is called a (metaphorical) polytheory.

It is known that the choice of axioms of a theory affects the size of proofs, so that even the simplest facts will require very long derivations, or statements about relatively small objects will require enormous formal proofs. For example, the boolean Pythagorean Triples problem was solved by presenting a 200 terabyte proof for the case $\{1, 2, \dots, 7825\}$ ¹, obtained in about 48,000 hours including verification [1]. We want to outline a workaround for at least part of the problem of long proofs through the definition of polytheory.

In order to reduce the complexity of proofs in a theory T , the idea of representing T as a set of several subtheories, $\{T'_i : i \in I\}$, with different axiomatics is proposed. The following considerations form our basis:

(1) if a short derivation of theorem ϕ is impossible from one set of axioms, then the possibility of a short derivation of ϕ from another set is not excluded; (2) finding a consistent axiomatics for a smaller set of formulas turns out to be easier than finding a consistent system of axioms for a larger set of ones; (3) it is easier to find a system of axioms in which not all the derived formulas will be formulas of T , and to extract the necessary formulas, use the appropriate procedure.

All of the above, together with the general logic of the fragments, forms a metaphorical polytheory. Sometimes the general logic of the fragments will be replaced by a simple union of sets of subtheory formulas. Let us refine the idea.

Definition 1 (metaphor of theory). Let there be consistent theories T, U , subtheories $T' \subset T, U' \subseteq U$, their languages $\mathcal{L}_T, \mathcal{L}_U$ and sets of sentences $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}_T}, \Sigma_{\mathcal{L}_U}$ in these languages respectively. T', U' are related by a bijection

$$f : T' \rightarrow U', \quad f = g|_{T'}, \quad g : \Sigma_{\mathcal{L}_T} \rightarrow \Sigma_{\mathcal{L}_U}$$

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¹The set $\{1, \dots, 7824\}$ can be partitioned into two parts, such that no part contains a Pythagorean triple, while this is impossible for $\{1, \dots, 7825\}$ [1].

(f is the restriction of g to T') such that: the consistency of T' with respect to U' is preserved —

$$\alpha' \in T', \beta' \in U', f^{-1}(\beta') \neq \neg\alpha'$$

for all $\alpha' \in T', \beta' \in U'$; but the property

$$(1) \quad \alpha \in T \setminus T', \beta \in U \setminus U', g^{-1}(\beta) = \neg\alpha, \neg\alpha \in T \text{ or } \neg\alpha \in \Sigma_{\mathcal{L}_T}$$

is allowed for all/some α and β . (Theories T and U are mutually consistent on subtheories T' and U' , but mutual contradiction on $T \setminus T'$ and $U \setminus U'$ is not forbidden.) Then U is a *metaphor for the theory T* with the notation $\text{Mph}(U/T)$. \triangleleft

Definition 2 (metaphorical decomposition, metaphorical polytheory). The decomposition of a theory T into a system of subtheories

$$\mathbf{T} = \{T'_i : T'_i \subset T, T = \bigcup_i T'_i, i \in I\},$$

for which there exists a system of metaphors

$$\mathbf{U} = \{U_i : \text{Mph}(U_i/T), f_i : U'_i \rightarrow T'_i, U'_i \subseteq U_i, i \in I\},$$

is a *metaphorical decomposition of the theory T* , and the tuple

$$\text{Pth}(T) = (T, \mathbf{T}, \mathbf{U}, L_T),$$

where L_T is the logic of deriving formulas of the theory T (when appropriate — simply union subtheories T'_i) based on the systems \mathbf{T} and \mathbf{U} , is a (*metaphorical*) *polytheory of the theory T* or simply a *polytheory of T* . \triangleleft

As an example of the above definitions we can take Skolem arithmetic, S , Presburger arithmetic, P , and the idea of a logic common to them. Each separately is a metaphor for the arithmetic of natural numbers, A . If $\sigma \in S$, $\pi \in P$, then $\sigma \star \pi$, \star — a logical connective, will be a formula in the language \mathcal{L}_T of the logic L_T , as is the formula $\neg(\sigma \star \pi)$; if λ and κ are formulas of \mathcal{L}_T , then the formula $\lambda \star \kappa$ will also be a formula of the language \mathcal{L}_T ; and further in the standard manner of defining well-formed formulas. The logic appropriate to the formal grammar described will be the general logic L_T . We do not know whether we are able to obtain the entire arithmetic of natural numbers or only a part of it by such methods, but perhaps we have the possibility of obtaining some decidable subsets of A through combined work with the decidable arithmetics of Skolem and Presburger.

Although many researchers will find the resolution of the property (1) suspicious, the author considers it very promising in finding short proofs, even taking into account the cost of finding an efficient choice of a subset of $U' \subseteq U$ so that there is no contradiction ($\alpha' = f^{-1}(\beta') \in T'$ and $(\neg\alpha' = f^{-1}(\gamma')) \in T', \beta', \gamma' \in U'$).

Our note does not claim that any long proof of any theory, including the example at the beginning, will become short in polytheory. However, we assume that there are many cases where our approach is justified, despite the need to find metaphors and create their general logic.

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